

ing on different compounds. Maximum zone of inhibition was observed in compound having R=*p*-hydroxyphenyl against *S. citreus* (23 mm), R=*m*-hydroxyphenyl against *S. aureus* (38 mm), R=4-pyridyl against *S. albus* (26 mm), R=phenyl against *E. coli* (27 mm). It was however observed that the fungi *A. niger* and *P. chrysogenum* were moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

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Synthesis of some Indole Derivatives

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INDOLE derivatives have marked hypotensive¹, anthelmintic², antibacterial³ and antiparkinsonian⁴ activities. 1,3- and 1,4-dizaepinoindoles are potent tranquilisers, sedative and antidepressants⁵⁻⁹. The substitution at 3-position in indole nucleus markedly affects hypotensive activity. Here, we report the

synthesis of some new 1,2,3-trisubstituted-indole derivatives.

The starting compound used for the synthesis of desired indole derivatives was *N*-cyanoethyl aromatic amine (2) which on condensation with α -benzoyl ethyl bromide followed by cyclodehydration in the presence of P_2O_5 in xylene gave *N*-cyanoethyl-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (3). The disappearance of quartet due to methine protons at δ 5.2 and appearance of $C_{\alpha}-CH_3$ protons at δ 2.5 indicated the cyclisation. The reduction of 3 either with $LiAlH_4$ in THF or Raney nickel in hydrazine gave *N*-propylamino-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4). The appearance of doublet in the ir spectra at $3\ 300\ cm^{-1}$ indicated the reduction of $C\equiv N$ group to CH_2NH_2 group. The compound 4 further reacted with various compounds having different structural moieties (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Hitachi spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. All the compounds were satisfactorily analysed for C, H and N. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

4-Methyl-N-cyanoethyl-p-toluidine (2): A mixture of *p*-toluidine (53.5 g, 0.5 mol) and acrylonitrile (26.5 g, 0.5 mol) and cupric acetate monohydrate (2.5 g) was heated under reflux for 0.5 h at 100 and 140° for 3 h. The dark reaction mixture was distilled under reduced pressure to remove the unreacted *p*-toluidine. On cooling, the separated solid on recrystallisation from ethanol gave 2 (40 g, 53%), m.p. 102° (Found: C, 82.15; H, 8.13; N, 9.50. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2$ requires: C, 82.19; H, 8.21; N, 9.58%); λ_{max} (ethanol) 265 and 300 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 200–3 300 (NH), 2 250 ($C\equiv N$), 1 700 ($C=O$) and 1 600 cm^{-1} ($C=C$); δ (TFA) 2.1 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.8 (2H, t, CH_2CN), 3.7 (2H, t, NCH_2) and 7.1 (5H, s, Ar H); $m/z M^+$ 160.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED-N-PROPYLAMINO-2,5-DIMETHYL-3-PHENYLINDOLE (4)

Compd.	R	R'	Mol. formula	Yield	M.P. °C	δ (ppm)
4a	H	COCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O	53	>300	1.1 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.1 (OH, s, ArCH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.55 (3H, s, NHCOCH ₃), 2.65 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 3.7 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (8H, m, ArH), 8.28 (1H, s, br, NHCO, exchangeable with D ₂ O).
4b	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂	55	>280	1.1 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.15 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.5 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.1 (6H, s, 2 × NOH ₂), 3.7 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (8H, m, ArH).
4c	H	CONHPh	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O	60	175	1.12 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.2 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.7 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.65 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7-8 (13H, m, ArH), 8.2-8.4 (2H, s, br, 2NHCO).
4d	H	CH ₂ CONH ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₂ O	56	>280	1.13 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.12 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.17 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.6 (4H, m, OH ₂ N), 3.65 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 4.2 (1H, s, br, NH), 7.1-7.8 (8H, m, ArH), 7.9 (2H, s, CONH ₂).
4e	H	COPh	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	65	85	1.11 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.11 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.65 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.65 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7.1-8.1 (13H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, br, NHCO).
4f	R R'	=CH-C ₆ H ₄ OH	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O	69	105	1.1 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.12 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.65 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.7 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7-7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, C=OH), 9.5 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D ₂ O).
4g	R R'	=CH-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ N ₂	69	80	1.12 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.10 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.60 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.1 (6H, s, N(CH ₃) ₂), 3.72 (2H, t, NOH ₂), 7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, C=OH).
4h	H	CH ₂ - -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	55	120	1.1 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.15 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.6 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.65 (2H, t, CH ₂ N), 3.8 (2H, s, CH ₂), 4.2 (1H, s, NH), 4.5 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7-7.8 (12H, m, ArH).
4i	H	CSNHPH	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ S	50	205	1.11 (2H, m, OH ₂), 2.15 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 2.22 (3H, s, C ₂ -OH ₂), 2.62 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 3.6 (2H, t, OH ₂ N), 5.2 (1H, s, br, NH), 7-7.8 (13H, m, ArH), 8.2 (2H, s, br, 2NH).

N-Cyanoethyl-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (3): A solution of 2 (2.30 g, 0.2 mol) in alcohol (50 ml) and α -benzoyl ethyl bromide (10 g, 0.09 mol) to which few drops of triethylamine were added, was heated on a water-bath for ~24 h, cooled and distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was heated under reflux with P₂O₅ in dry xylene for 8 h. The hot solution was filtered and xylene was removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was recrystallised from alcohol to give 3 (20 g, 36%), m.p. 88° (Found: C, 83.16; H, 6.50;

N, 10.12. C₂₁H₁₈N₂ requires: C, 83.21; H, 6.56; N, 10.21%; λ_{max} (ethanol) 265 and 285 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 2250 (C≡N) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (TFA) 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 2.8 (2H, t, CH₂CN), 3.75 (2H, t, NCH₂) and 7.15-7.8 (8H, m, ArH); m/z M⁺ 274.

N-Propylamino-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4; R=R'=H): To a solution of LiAlH₄ (7.6 g, 0.2 mol) in dry ether (30 ml), a solution of 3 (23.5 g, 0.2 mol) in dry ether (30 ml) was added and stirred

magnetically for 1.5 h. Then ice was added to decompose excess of LiAlH_4 and the ether layer was washed with sodium tartarate solution (50 ml). Ether on evaporation gave solid which when recrystallised from alcohol gave **4** (12 g, 51%), m.p. 75° (Found: C, 81.75; H, 7.86; N, 10.01). $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 81.01; H, 7.91; N, 10.07%; ν_{max} (nujol) 3300 (NH_2), 1600 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1500 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$); δ (TFA) 1.0 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.15 (3H, s, C_2-CH_3), 2.6 (2H, t, CH_2NH_2), 3.7 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.2 (2H, s, NH) and 7.05–7.7 (8H, m, ArH); M^+ , 278 (0.2%), 187 (50%), 160 (25%), 120 (100%), 105 (15%), 91 (33%), 77 (17%) and 65 (10%).

Compounds **4b**, **4e**, **4g**, **4h** and **4i** (Table 1) were prepared according to general method used for the preparation of **4c**.

N-(N-Phenylcarbamylamino propyl)-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4c): A mixture of **4** (0.139 g; 0.0005 mol) and phenylisocyanate (0.0595 g, 0.0005 mol) in THF (10 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~5 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid formed was recrystallised from ethanol to give **4c** (0.158 g, 80%), m.p. 175° (Found: C, 78.53; H, 6.75; N, 10.55). $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires: C, 78.58; H, 6.80; N, 10.57%.

The following experimental procedure forms a general method for the preparation of **4a**, **4d** and **4f**.

N-(N-4-Hydroxybenzylideneamino propyl)-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylindole (4f): A mixture of **4** (0.139 g, 0.0005 mol) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.062 g, 0.0005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was refluxed for ~6 h, and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained which when recrystallised from ethanol to give **4f** (0.131 g, 69%), m.p. 105° (Found: C, 81.60; H, 6.75; N, 7.30). $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires: C, 81.76; H, 6.80; N, 7.32%.

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Synthesis of 2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-(substituted-phenylureido)-s-triazine Derivatives and Study of their Antibacterial Activity

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UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities, such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anaesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants. Salicylamide has been claimed to be more potent than aspirin. Salicylamide has a marked anthelmintic, antispasmodic, antipyretic and sedative action^{4,5}.

To study the antibacterial⁶ activity of compounds of the type **1** were synthesised by the condensation of cyanuric chloride (0.1 M) and *o*-anisidine (0.1 M). The resulted product was afforded to react with salicylamide in equimolecular proportion. The compound obtained was made to condense with various phenyl ureas to get the compounds of the type **1**.

Experimental

2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine: *o*-Anisidine (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added to a well stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone at $0-5^\circ$. pH of the solution was maintained 7 by adding aqueous 2% NaOH during the reaction. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h. Crushed ice was then added to it and filtered, and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (86%), m.p. 126° .

2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-chloro-s-triazine: Salicylamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetone and 5% NaOH solution was added dropwise during 1.5 h to a mechanically stirred solution of 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol) in dioxane at 35° . The temperature was gradually increased to 45° during 2 h. pH was maintained by addition of aqueous NaOH. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. It was added in crushed ice and HCl solution (2%). The compound obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene, (76%), m.p. 162° .

General method for preparation of 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yloxy)-6-(phenylureido)-s-